

Promoting Bottom-up Dialogue:

A Study of Community-Level Dialogue Experiences in Zimbabwe

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Cover image: “Out and About” by Barry Lungu

Executive Summary

Calls for dialogue to address Zimbabwe's multi-layered political, social and economic crises have been numerous, repeated and diverse. Calls for *national* dialogue have been particularly frequent, usually precipitated by cycles of unrest and conflict. Yet, the attempts to date have consistently failed to sustain long-term activity and results.

At the community level, by contrast, there is a rich culture of dialogue to engage and resolve disputes. Community members regularly convene to address social and economic issues through alternative dispute resolution processes such as organised consultation, negotiation and mediation processes. Though varying in scope and subject, these dialogues represent a bottom-up approach where local constituents are not just participants but drivers of conversation and change.

This research contains findings from an investigation of 13 diverse community dialogues in Zimbabwe that took place between 2017 and 2023 at the ward, village, or district level and considers lessons that can inform future initiatives at the national level. The dialogues were convened by different actors, including community leaders from different political parties, business associations, industry councils and civil society organisations.

Research interviews and focus group sessions interrogated factors such as dialogue context, pre-conditions, scope, participation, format, barriers, success factors, short-term outcomes and long-term impacts.

Key findings

The case studies highlighted the positive impact of community dialogue in Zimbabwe; particularly how it fostered unity, facilitated mindset shifts and empowered communities to address their daily challenges from a shared understanding.

Context preconditions and scope: Findings showed that it is important to contextualise dialogue processes within the social norms and cultural context of the specific community, such that initiatives fit community-specific needs and sensitivities. At the same time, the research highlighted that perfect conditions for starting a dialogue are rare, so it is important to just get started.

Dialogue convenors: The research found that convening power lies with trusted and established institutions, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) or community leaders who then play a leading role in addressing the local issues at hand. Proactive engagement by community leaders with relevant stakeholders was found to be especially determinant to desired outcomes, and was enhanced through technical support.

Dialogue actors: The research showed the importance of engaging critical stakeholders early in the dialogue process. In particular, the involvement and endorsement of community leaders was crucial for success, especially when accompanied by inclusive engagement and narratives, and by communicating dialogue outcomes.

Dialogue structures and frameworks: Effective dialogue formats were characterised by a collaborative agenda-setting process, positive vision casting, careful process design, and proactive use of digital platforms. Findings also highlighted that location of the dialogue is another critical consideration in order to ensure transparency, accessibility and security.

Participation and inclusivity: Findings revealed that diversity and representation of groups in the community helped to capture multiple perspectives. Successful dialogues included those who were directly affected by the issue, with attention to youth participation and incorporating and strengthening their skills.

Overcoming barriers: Multiple barriers to effective dialogue were identified, including apathy, logistical and financial constraints, polarisation and reluctance to address long-standing social issues. Overcoming these barriers required intensive trust-building and sustained efforts led by a trusted convenor who focussed on shifting the narrative to win-win outcomes. Fostering partnerships was critical in addressing the financial and logistical constraints of participants.

Implementing dialogue outcomes: The successful implementation of agreements hinged on effective post-dialogue communication, feedback loops with appropriate channels, clearly defined responsibilities and robust mechanisms for monitoring.

Sustaining long-term success: Findings showed that a successful outcome must be well defined and measurable. Collaborations and partnerships enhanced outcomes and a continual spotlight on dialogue successes helped to promote convergence on a dialogue culture.

Recommendations for enhancing national-level dialogue.

This study finds that issues identified at the community level can be elevated to the national level in Zimbabwe using a bottom-up approach, where concerns are escalated from the ward level to the district and provincial levels before reaching the national level. Depending on circumstances, any of the intermediate levels may be skipped.

An alternative approach could involve civic organisations and other relevant institutions replicating and multiplying the same dialogue nationwide in a coordinated manner.

In either case, the following strategies identified in the practices of Zimbabwe's community-level dialogues can usefully inform national-level dialogue initiatives:

- Focussing on galvanising issues to catalyse dialogue and unite polarised communities.
- Identifying strategic entry points and locations for dialogue.
- Initiating national conversations in locations with a historical or economic significance to the dialogue.
- Using dialogue champions to drive narratives and build support or buy-in towards the dialogue agenda.

A broad-based civic platform in Zimbabwe could play a key role in taking forward the lessons of this study and building inclusive dialogue nationally from what already exists in robust form locally.

I. Introduction

National-level dialogue in Zimbabwe has usually been precipitated by unrest and often characterised by conflict. Since the 2008 Global Political Agreement (GPA), which ushered in the Government of National Unity (GNU), no significant national-level dialogue initiative has achieved long-term, credible or impactful results that are beneficial to the broader populace.

By contrast, a robust culture of community dialogue exists at the local level in Zimbabwe. Local leaders convene dialogues focused on “bread and butter” issues. In some instances, community dialogues are convened to resolve conflict. While varying in scope and subject—from access to health and education to service delivery and economic disputes— these dialogues represent a bottom-up approach and experience wherein local constituents are not just participants, but drivers of change.

Such dialogues are inherently rooted in Zimbabwe’s traditional culture, as encapsulated by the Shona or Ndebele term “*Dare*,” or “*iDale*“, meaning a place for discussion and a tribunal for ideas. These terms reflect a commonly practiced but little-acknowledged culture of dialogue among Zimbabweans. These have the potential to provide critical insights that can be useful in bolstering and enriching national-level dialogue efforts in the country.

This study, commissioned by the [Institute for Integrated Transitions](#) (IFIT), offers detailed analysis of 13 cases of community-level dialogue. It seeks to 1) identify successful positive strategies for non-partisan, community-level dialogue and 2) consider their potential replication at the national level to help catalyse meaningful issue-based dialogue among different actors, including political ones.

By delving into the nuances of these local dialogues, the study offers insights into the mechanisms that foster agreement and resolution, the challenges and barriers encountered, and the strategies that drive long-term success. It is through this underexplored lens that we can begin to understand how the power of dialogue can be harnessed to forge a path toward a shared destiny of a more unified, resilient and prosperous Zimbabwe for all.

II. Methodology

Key Research Questions

This research aims to answer the following questions:

- What **mechanisms** (e.g., local, national, traditional) exist to help Zimbabweans resolve community-level disputes and reach agreements?
- What is the **typical structure and composition** of community-level dialogues in Zimbabwe? Which methods (e.g., mediation, conciliation, arbitration) are most effective for reaching agreements?
- How are these **dialogues initiated** and what role, if any, do intermediaries play in facilitating community-level dialogues and resolving disputes?
- On what issues are **agreements** being reached between citizens and local leaders and between villages, wards and/or districts from opposing social, economic or political parties and from different ethnic and religious groups and sectors?
- How are the resolutions from community-level dialogues **implemented**? What roles do local, **traditional and/or national mechanisms** play to ensure agreements are not breached? How are failures in implementation addressed?
- What **strategies or lessons** from community-level dialogues can be leveraged or replicated at the national level to help catalyse dialogue among the country's political actors from across the political divide (e.g., political settlement) and among Zimbabweans (e.g., national dialogue)?

Key Definitions and Terminology

For purposes of this research, “community dialogue” is defined as:

A forum, meeting or convening that draws participants from various sections of a community and creates the opportunity for exchanging information and perspectives, clarifying viewpoints, and developing solutions to issues of interest to the community.¹

The different types of dialogue examined in this research are classified into mediation, negotiation or consultation, defined as follows for the purposes of this research:

1. Common Ground Institute, September 2017, Community Mediation Basics. Available [Online] at: [\[1\]](#)

- **Mediation:** a process whereby two or more parties seek to reach an amicable settlement of their dispute with the assistance of a third-party mediator accepted by them (source: IFIT).
- **Negotiation:** a process whereby two or more parties attempt to reach an amicable settlement of their dispute through direct dialogue (source: IFIT).
- **Consultation:** a participatory process in which groups affected by a proposed policy or decision are given a meaningful opportunity to articulate their ideas and concerns.

Discussion formats common in community dialogues and identified in the case studies include:

- **Round tables:** where a facilitator keeps the discussions moving around various speakers and topics to gain different perspectives.
- **Town halls:** where an idea is presented, and participants voice their opinions and ask questions.
- **Panels:** where an expert panel leads discussions and participants engage through comments and questions.
- **Open discussions:** where the dialogue involves question and answer (Q&A) format, and the agenda is fluid.

Research Phases

The research was conducted in four phases: 1) preliminary research and prioritisation of cases; 2) data collection; 3) analysis and reporting; and 4) testing and validation.

Phase 1: Preliminary research and prioritisation of cases

Initial research involved compiling a database of 25 dialogues that occurred across various villages, wards, and districts throughout Zimbabwe. These dialogues were facilitated by a range of actors, including the ruling party, opposition parties, civil society, churches, community leaders, and/or industry associations. These were across a wide array of topics encompassing social, political, and economic issues. Thirteen dialogues were ultimately selected for analysis. The case studies (listed [here](#)) were carefully chosen to represent diverse geographic locations, the demographic diversity of Zimbabwe, and a range of topics.

Phase 2: Data collection

For each selected case study, the dialogue convenor(s) and, in most cases, at least one other participant, were interviewed. Interviews were conducted according to a framework that was developed to assess the dialogues against six factors (listed below in Phase 3). Interviews were done either virtually or in person. [Annex A](#) details the questions that were posed to both convenors and participants about the different aspects of the dialogue and [Annex B](#) details the list of interviewees.

Phase 3: Analysis and reporting

Each of the case studies was assessed against an interview framework that included:

- 1. Context and Scope:** an assessment of the events that led to the need for dialogue and focus on the issue that was addressed.
- 2. Participation and Inclusivity:** an evaluation of how participation and inclusivity were built into the process, from the planning stages to implementation.
- 3. Structure and Framework:** an analysis of the discussion format and the mechanisms focussing on how the dialogues were led, moderated or facilitated.
- 4. Barriers to Dialogue:** any roadblock or impediment that temporarily or permanently stalled or interrupted the dialogue process.
- 5. Success Drivers and Indicators:** identification of factors that influenced any positive outcome.
- 6. Outcomes and Long-Term Impact:** an analysis of the impact the dialogue had on the core issue and an assessment on how the results were sustained.

Phase 4: Testing and validation

Following the prior phases of work, an initial report was produced to summarise the findings and provide an analysis of the dialogues. This report served as the basis for a series of focus group meetings aimed at discussing its contents and validating key lessons. The meetings were attended by convenors from the case studies and included some community dialogue experts.

III. Analysis of Community Dialogues

This section presents a comprehensive analysis of 13 community-level dialogues conducted across Zimbabwe. The selection of these 13 cases was important because there is a representation of various issues, inclusion based on geographic location of communities, different dialogue formats and dialogue convenors. Each case study includes a summary of the dialogue process and key details such as the issues addressed, format used, key actors, barriers and challenges encountered, success factors, and outcomes achieved. By examining the successes and challenges, we identify critical factors that contribute to effective community engagement and local conflict resolution.

List of Selected Community Dialogues

#	Dialogue	Location	Level	Date
1	Bulawayo Leather Value Chain Consultation	Bulawayo	City	March 2023
2	Domboshava School Fees Negotiation	Domboshava	Ward	November 2022
3	Mbare Disability-Sensitive TerminologyW Roundtable	Mbare	Ward	April 2023
4	Enhancing Harare’s Early Childhood Development Policies	Harare	City	2019 - 2022
5	Empowering Epworth’s Youth – Dialogues for Change	Epworth	Ward	April 2023
6	Rimuka’s Flood Solution Journey	Rimuka	Ward	January – March 2022
7	Empowering Girls – Tsholotsho Service Delivery Dialogues	Tsholotsho	Village	April 2023
8	Ending Child Marriage – Chiredzi’s Commitment	Chiredzi	Village	2017 – present
9	Nkulumane Resolution – Vendors vs. Bulawayo Council	Nkulumane	Ward	August 2022
10	Mambo Township’s Water Crisis Response	Mambo	Ward	2019 – 2020
11	Challenge to Monetary Policy – Kadoma Busines Community	Kadoma	City	August 2020
12	Crime Resolution in a Harare Neighbourhood	Harare	Ward	April – June 2018
13	Penhalonga Residents Confront Mining Company	Penhalonga	Town	2017 – present

Case 1: Bulawayo Leather Value Chain Consultation

Stakeholders at the Leather Stakeholders Indaba engaging in roundtable discussions on value chain issues.

In April 2023, Solidaridad, a global NGO dedicated to promoting sustainable supply chains and enhancing the livelihoods of workers and farmers across various industries, co-hosted a Leather Stakeholders *Indaba* (‘meeting’ in Ndebele) in Bulawayo. The five-day consultation brought together diverse players from the leather value chain. Bulawayo, a designated special economic zone for the leather industry, offers specific privileges and tax exemptions to leather businesses in the area.

Zimbabwe’s Ministry of Industry and Commerce launched the Zimbabwe Leather Sector Strategy (2021–2030) in April 2021, recognising the need for an apex body to coordinate the national leather value chain. The Zimbabwe Leather Development Council (ZLDC), established in 2013, played a coordinating role for several years but had yet to be formally instituted as a national council.

For years, the leather value chain remained highly fragmented, plagued by a lack of trust among industry players. The envisaged formalisation of ZLDC had been a divisive issue, with some players not recognising the council’s authority, which led to misalignment and regression for the industry in general. The *Indaba* aimed to address these issues by facilitating discussions on various topics, including environmental and safety concerns, emerging technologies and supply chain issues. The discussions were led by officials from the Bulawayo offices of various government agencies and industry association leaders.

Solidaridad partnered with the ZLDC secretariat for the *Indaba*, drawing on Solidaridad’s programme planning and project implementation experience. One of the primary objectives was to emphasise the importance of establishing inclusive roundtable discussions and public platforms for dialogue within the industry. Participants noted that the *Indaba* fostered frank exchanges, in a refreshing departure from previous meetings.

Jacob Nyathi, the secretary of ZLDC, highlighted the impact of the *Indaba*, which included a clear position from the Ministry of Industry and Commerce regarding next steps in the formalisation process. The discussions among government officials and value chain members identified potential obstacles, paving the way for a road-map to guide the formation of the apex body and the strengthening of the industry.

Case 1 Analysis Table	
Issue	Lack of coordination, alignment and trust among players within Zimbabwe’s fragmented leather value chain and concerning the formalisation of the Zimbabwe Leather Development Council (ZLDC).
Convenor	Solidaridad and ZLDC
Date	March 2023
Mechanism	Consultation
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ZLDC • Farmers, abattoirs, hide merchants, tanneries, manufacturers and retailers • Representatives from key ministries and government agencies (e.g., National Social Security Authority, Environmental Management Agency, Industry and Commerce, Finance and Economic Development) • National University of Science and Technology
Structure and composition	The meeting was attended by about 50 participants. There were presentations followed by roundtable discussions around multiple agenda items. Each item was chaired by the relevant expert or official representative.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of key obstacles to ZLDC formalisation and endorsement of a roadmap for formalisation. • Commitment to prioritising waste management with Environmental Management Agency support and adopting international standards in waste, effluent and environmental management. • Identification of industry innovation and value addition opportunities.
Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lingering tensions and lack of trust among certain stakeholders. • Disagreements concerning the policy for the export of rawhides within specific value chain sectors. • A few influential industry players declined participation, citing different reasons, with some frustrated by the lack of recognition of the ZLDC by formal processes.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitators resolved tensions by promoting ownership and open discussions on past issues, aligning parties towards common goals • The convenors emphasised the importance of unity and inspiring collective action to seize missed opportunities. • Government and institutional support, particularly from entities such as Solidaridad, was crucial for funding, planning and strengthening collaborative structures. • Effective facilitation and shared commitments led to actionable resolutions, fostering unified efforts for future success.

Case 2: Domboshava School Fees Negotiation

When retired nurse Josephine Chibanda wanted to open a clinic in the Domboshava community, she requested a meeting with the *sabhuku* ('village head' in Shona). After she presented her vision for a community clinic and made a request for land, the *sabhuku* informed her that the community's greatest need was a school. He explained that a clinic would be useful, but pointed out that the closest school was more than 10 km away and many children had to cross a river to reach it, which would flood in the rainy season.

Chibanda decided to change course and agreed to build a school instead. That initial consultative dialogue with the *sabhuku* directed her to the true issue in the community, and she understood the value of solving real problems. Despite being a nurse by profession, Chibanda started a dialogue to establish Victory Christian Primary School, a non-profit organisation. Two years later, the school educates 45 children from early childhood development level to Grade 2.

With the support of the *sabhuku*, Chibanda rallied the community behind her vision to build the school and then expand its classrooms. A dialogue she convened in November 2022 involved a tense negotiation process over school fees. Other schools in the area do not charge fees, whereas Chibanda was asking for term fees of US\$25 to cover basic expenses such as salaries and food. To succeed, the dialogue needed community members to explore a new mindset, while Chibanda had to justify the requirement.

Whilst the amount may seem nominal, some of the parents had two or more children enrolled at the school and the financial burden was not easy to bear. At the end of the process, a compromise was reached: the parents agreed to pay US\$20 per term per child and committed to participate in building and fundraising activities to ensure all targets were met and the school could run smoothly.

By the end of 2023, the school had two classrooms and an administration block. The school has not received funding from any donor and all progress has been a collective effort by the parents and the school leadership. Through a mix of consultations and negotiations, Victory Christian Primary School is serving the Dom-boshava community in an impactful way.

Case 2 Analysis Table	
Issue	Disagreement over Victory Christian Primary School fees to cover essential expenses and ensure accessible education for children in the Dom-boshava community.
Convenor	School founder
Date	November 2022
Mechanism	Negotiation
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School founder • Village head • School staff • Parents
Structure and composition	About 25 parents, or half of all parents, attended the meeting. The school founder led an open discussion where a proposal was formulated. The proposal was discussed until a consensus was reached.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A significant majority of parents supported the initiative, agreeing to pay US\$20 in term fees and volunteer their time and building materials for the school's development. • A small number of parents who could not commit to the fees made the decision to withdraw their children from the school. • Parents took the initiative to create a committee to manage school affairs and ensure implementation of resolutions.
Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only half of the parents engaged in the dialogue, hindering full participation • Some parents, unable or unwilling to pay fees, pressed for a fee moratorium, creating a challenge in reaching a consensus.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The school founder shifted parents from a donor mindset to a community-led approach, fostering ownership and involvement. • Strong support from the village head for fees and dialogues enhanced community engagement. • Training in dialogue and conflict resolution for the convenor facilitated effective communication and problem-solving. • A strong sense of pride and ownership within the community spurred further development, evidenced by the addition of classrooms following successful fee negotiations. • Community resolutions and progress were effectively communicated verbally, ensuring widespread understanding and support.

Case 3: Mbare Disability-Sensitive Language Roundtable

I Am Zimbabwe Trust is an organisation dedicated to transforming the lives of youth in urban and rural communities through educational programmes and community engagement activities. Its mission intersects with the goals of the Zimbabwe International Disability Association (ZIDA), which focuses on addressing various issues affecting persons with disabilities, including inclusion, access and reasonable accommodation.

In April 2023, staff from the two organisations came together for a roundtable discussion. It had come to their attention that discriminatory and derogatory terms were prevalent in conversations involving individuals with disabilities in Mbare.

Tinashe Rutambo of I Am Zimbabwe Trust said that the goal of the meeting was to brainstorm interventions that would raise awareness within the Mbare community about using proper terminology when addressing or referring to individuals with disabilities. Rutambo noted, “In some cases, people have no idea what the appropriate language is. It’s our responsibility to sensitise and educate them about the correct terms to use.”

Prior to the meeting, the organisations signed a memorandum of understanding (MOU) that committed staff to regular meetings and ensuring that their community initiatives complemented each other. They acknowledged the importance of fostering a culture of dialogue surrounding disability inclusion, despite lacking a dedicated budget for the project.

The roundtable discussion was led by facilitators from both organisations. According to Trevor Nyathi of ZIDA, the participants reached the consensus that the most effective way to convey the message about appropriate terminology would be through the performing arts.

Following the meeting, a joint team, including community participants, developed an interactive play that would educate audiences on disability-sensitive language. As they lacked the funds required to perform the play throughout the community and produce a high-quality video to reach a broader audience, this specific intervention has not yet been implemented.

The process, however, brought to light many challenges faced by persons with disabilities. Participants noticed that men in the community were increasingly abandoning children born with disabilities, leaving mothers with the sole responsibility of care. As a result, the organisations resolved to engage with men in the community to discuss the issue and provide support and education that would enable them to fulfil their parental responsibilities. This initiative was successfully implemented in 2023.

Case 3 Analysis Table	
Issue	Prevalent use of disability-insensitive language when addressing or referring to persons with disabilities within the Mbare community.
Convenors	I Am Zimbabwe Trust and Zimbabwe International Disability Association (ZIDA)
Date	2023
Mechanism	Roundtable
Key actors	I Am Zimbabwe Trust and ZIDA
Structure and composition	Roundtable discussion
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement to produce a community play for language awareness. • Commitment to spotlight the language issue in public interactions. • Decision to address additional concerns, including dialogues on fathers abandoning children with disabilities.
Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited funds for activities and materials. • Cultural and social norms that stigmatise and discriminate against people with disabilities. • Difficulty engaging certain community members, like men, on sensitive issues. • Complexities in coordinating efforts between organisations. • Difficulty in sustaining initiatives due to logistical or financial constraints.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Despite financial constraints, initial meetings and pre-production moved forward without a budget, highlighting adaptability and resourcefulness. • A formalised MOU between the two organisations, rooted in a strong history of collaboration, was a foundational success factor. • The convenors, skilled in dialogue and community engagement, leveraged their experience to explore creative solutions. • Effective communication was ensured by circulating meeting minutes among attendees and the organisations feeding information back to their members, fostering transparency and inclusion.

Case 4: Enhancing Harare's Early Childhood Development Policies

In 2019, the Zimbabwe Network of Early Childhood Development Actors (ZINECDA) embarked on a series of consultative meetings aimed at establishing a platform for information sharing, strategic planning and the enhancement of policies on early childhood development in Harare.

These meetings were thoughtfully designed as inclusive multi-stakeholder forums, bringing together civil society organisations, educators and government officials. The primary objective was to advocate for improvements in school readiness policies and increased investment in early child development. The meetings incorporated expert presentations with comprehensive plenary discussions, which ensured active participation.

Fast forward nearly three years and significant policy shifts have become apparent. Today, there is a freshly formulated National Early Learning Policy that explicitly addresses early childhood development.²

Hazvinei Mushonga, an administrator at ZINECDA, attributes this achievement to the unwavering commitment of all the stakeholders, who remained aligned and steadfast in their mission. She underscored the collaborative nature of the endeavour, which demanded sustained effort over several years. Importantly, the process was characterised by inclusivity, with dialogues conducted across the 10 provinces in Zimbabwe.

2. The Sunday Mail, 20 April 2023, *New National Early Learning Policy Approved*, [Online] Available at: [\[2\]](#).

As the consultations evolved, fresh challenges were identified, and new implementing partners were brought into the fold. The discourse surrounding policy improvement has not only persisted but also expanded through workshops, lobbying initiatives and advocacy campaigns, spanning grassroots to national level.

Case 4 Analysis Table	
Issue	Inadequate policies to support early childhood development in Harare.
Convenors	Zimbabwe Network of Early Childhood Development Actors (ZINECDA)
Date	2019 – 2022
Mechanism	Consultation
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society organisations • Representatives of rural and urban municipalities • Parliamentarians • Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education
Structure and composition	The consultative meetings were attended by multiple stakeholders. They usually included presentations led by subject matter experts, followed by plenary sessions.
Outcomes	A National Early Learning Policy that addresses early childhood development and is aligned to Zimbabwe’s Constitution.
Barriers and challenges	There was a broad agenda and many issues that needed to be addressed at multiple levels. This made for a complex process that needed to be tackled incrementally.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders’ long-term commitment was essential for overcoming challenges and achieving project goals. • Unity among civil society organisations (sharing a common vision) significantly contributed to the initiative’s success. • Broad institutional support and funding underpinned successful implementation of the project. • Thorough dissemination and collaborative execution of meeting resolutions by partners fostered effective action and progress. • Frequent publication of research and opinion pieces by partners raised awareness and support.

Case 5: Empowering Epworth's Youth – Dialogues for Change

Kunashe Foundation youth peer educators conducting a financial literacy training in Epworth after consultative meetings.

Community leaders in Epworth observed an increase in violence, substance abuse, teenage pregnancies and mental health challenges among the township's school-going youth. Eager to understand these issues and uncover their root causes, they enlisted the assistance of the Kunashe Foundation to organise and lead dialogues with young members of their community in April 2023.

The Kunashe Foundation is a youth-led non-profit organisation dedicated to promoting the socio-economic inclusion and well-being of women and young people. With years of experience in various Zimbabwean communities, the foundation boasts a team of youth peer educators trained to engage with young people.

The foundation convened a dialogue at Epworth Community School, a location chosen for its familiarity, safe atmosphere and open engagement with students. Situated near Epworth's centre, the school is operated by the Hands of Hope organisation.

The dialogue prompted rich discussions, with the youth candidly sharing their perspectives on a range of topics, from their attitudes towards drug use and pre-marital sex to their views on the current socio-economic and civil-political climate. They articulated the impact of their surroundings on their daily lives. Encouraged by their teachers to speak freely, the students contributed valuable insights.

Armed with a deeper understanding of the issues and a set of recommendations, the Kunashe Foundation met with community leaders to relay their findings. This enabled the leaders to better understand the social challenges within the community and help develop several programmes tailored to address the issues highlighted by the youth.

The programmes introduced by the Kunashe Foundation were shaped by these consultative processes. For example, the foundation responded to youth concerns

about socio-economic challenges by launching a series of age-appropriate financial literacy and entrepreneurship training sessions. It also celebrated the International Day of the Girl Child, focusing on leadership and wellness. The programmes enjoy the robust support of community leaders, who have consistently and actively participated in the initiatives.

Case 5 Analysis Table	
Issue	Increasing violence, drug and alcohol use, adolescent pregnancy and mental health challenges among school-going youth in Epworth.
Convenor	Kunashe Foundation
Date	April 2023
Mechanism	Consultation
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students (aged 10–18) • School teachers • Community leaders • Ward councillors • Kunashe Foundation staff
Structure and composition	About 40 students between the ages of 10 and 18 attended and were split into groups of about 12. Each group was led through a facilitated discussion. Information from the various sessions was collated.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussions provided a better understanding of young people’s views and day-to-day challenges. • Information from the dialogues informed community leaders, leading to proposed interventions in meetings with parents and businesses. • The Kunashe Foundation devised several programs of customised training sessions and awareness-raising campaigns addressing the issues. • The dialogues served as a valuable learning experience for the young people, enhancing their ability to articulate thoughts on economic and civic issues.
Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conversations sometimes stalled when sensitive topics such as drug use and sex were discussed, as some young people were reluctant to express themselves openly on such topics. • Community leaders who were present expressed some reservations about whether children and youth should discuss politics. • There was a wide age range and, in some cases, the younger children parroted the older children.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anticipation of sensitive topics, establishment of discussion rules, and assurance of a safe space by facilitators were key in navigating challenges. • Facilitators respected and addressed reservations, steering discussions clear of political commentary as necessary. • Conducting dialogues in safe, familiar youth environments fostered openness and effective communication. • The involvement of trained peer educators was pivotal in connecting with and engaging young participants meaningfully. • Teachers, through their daily interactions with students, brought valuable depth and context to the discussions.

Case 6: Rimuka's Flood Solution Journey

Photo by: Post on Sunday

For Kadoma Ward 17 Councillor Joyce Moyo and Kadoma Ward 13 Councillor Deven Levie, community dialogues are the cornerstone upon which they build their interactions with constituents. Both local authority representatives have regularly convened meetings with their constituents, primarily focusing on how residents can enhance their role in service delivery.

In ward meetings, the councillors have fostered an already vibrant culture of dialogue. The meetings are sometimes highly emotive, as residents express their frustrations concerning water shortages, inadequate street lighting and malfunctioning sewer systems, among other concerns.

To address the issue of street lighting, Moyo suggested that residents collaborate to install solar streetlights in certain areas to enhance visibility and combat crime. Residents received this proposal with lukewarm enthusiasm, as the Kadoma City Council charges residents for street lighting. They expected the city to solve the problem. Moyo explained that her ability to deliver solutions was constrained by the council's limited budget. "Many of the issues that frustrated the residents on a daily basis required funding – sewage, water supply and lighting. The city needs substantial infrastructure investment but lacks sufficient resources," she remarked.

Grappling with the similar issues, Levie noted the critical importance of inclusive dialogue in the consultation and feedback process with residents. He underscored the significance of dialogues that take place during council meetings, where many decisions stemming from primary dialogues with residents are discussed and put into action. Arguing for greater visibility of City Council officials to enhance residents' understanding of the complexities behind limited funds and subpar service delivery, he pointed to the example of Mutare City Council, where councillors have been livestreaming their council meetings for several years.

“When residents can tune into these council meetings and listen to the discussions, it will help them grasp the issues at hand. These are vital dialogues that residents should be able to follow,” Levie asserted. He revealed that plans to initiate live broadcasts of Kadoma City Council meetings are now in the advanced stages. He believes this will inject much-needed accountability and transparency into council affairs.

Community service delivery dialogues also spurred Levie to act on a recurring flooding issue in Rimuka. Each rainy season resulted in houses flooding due to poor drainage and inadequate planning. In early 2023, Levie began advocating for drainage work to commence a month before the rains – an approach that residents repeatedly highlighted in monthly feedback and community WhatsApp groups. Understanding the budgetary constraints, Levie collaborated with the City Council Engineering Department to expedite an early response, leading to the initiation of drainage work over 15 km. It was a gradual process, but it ultimately achieved the desired outcome.

While this marked a success for the community, service delivery dialogues continue, and Levie is quick to emphasise that there is still work to be done. “In 2024, we will establish Ward Development Committees led by residents,” said Levie. “We will also uphold the tradition of monthly feedback meetings. Dialogue is a fundamental aspect of our work, and progress would be impossible without it.”

Case 6 Analysis Table	
Issue	Recurring flooding caused by poor drainage and inadequate planning during the rainy season in the Rimuka township.
Convenor	Ward councillor
Date	January – March 2023
Mechanism	Consultations
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ward councillor • Community residents
Structure and composition	The ward councillor convened monthly meetings in his ward, to which residents came to hear feedback from council meetings, voice grievances and propose solutions.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A revamped drainage system in the ward, through collaboration with the City Council Engineering Department. • A new dialogue space for community members to voice grievances and collectively seek solutions.
Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ward councillors have been accustomed to traditional methods of addressing residents' grievances, with limited innovation and success. • Introducing a new implementation strategy at the council level required innovative dialogues, demands for extra funding and the engagement of relevant stakeholders for buy-in.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The councillor's proactive planning and early initiation of efforts before the rainy season were crucial for aligning resources and manpower within budgetary constraints. • Success was significantly driven by the consistency and proactive nature of the councillor's actions, underscored by a clear vision of the desired outcome.

Case 7: Empowering Girls – Tsholotsho Service Delivery Dialogues

The Girls Table convenes a meeting on voting rights with young women in Tsholotsho.

Tsholotsho, situated in one of Zimbabwe’s driest regions, has grappled with severe water shortages for decades, which were exacerbated by a 2017 breach in Gariya Dam.³ While water scarcity affects the entire community, its burden disproportionately falls on young women tasked with fetching water for their households.

While local authorities and civil society organisations have installed boreholes, residents note that they lack maintenance, frequently stop functioning and present contamination risks from rusty pipes and dirt.

Enter The Girls Table, a women-led organisation based in Bulawayo and mandated to amplify the voices of girls and young women on socio-economic and political issues. In April 2023, The Girls Table orchestrated a virtual roundtable discussion uniting young women from across the Matabeleland region to address the water crisis and explore collaborative solutions.

Eighteen-year-old Sikhonzeni Ndlovu, from Tsholotsho, encountered The Girls Table when she was invited to a town hall meeting on voting rights – an event attended by around 20 girls from the village. Reflecting on this experience, Ndlovu expressed her enthusiasm for engaging in civic discussions directly impacting her daily life, noting the rarity of such opportunities for young women like herself in community gatherings typically dominated by men and/or older women.

3. The Sunday News, 17 September 2017, *Tsholothso faces serious water shortage*, [Online] Available at: [\[3\]](#)

Subsequently, Ndlovu participated in an online talk show alongside other young women from Matabeleland, amplifying their voices in the ongoing discourse on water challenges. Hosted in Bulawayo and facilitated by a presenter, the talk show featured insights from a representative of the Bulawayo Progressive Residents Association. The dialogue not only fostered information exchange but also introduced a novel concept: empowering young girls to serve as community champions and advocate for their villages' rights at the grassroots level.

The virtual discussion ignited Ndlovu's interest, leading her to attend a media and information literacy training. Now, she hosts [her own podcast](#),⁴ sustaining the critical conversation on water scarcity by interviewing women affected by the situation. In a poignant episode broadcast in June 2023, two young mothers shared their struggles, detailing the arduous process of manually pumping a borehole for up to 30 minutes to yield a mere three buckets of often contaminated water.

These podcasts, disseminated across various social media platforms, serve as platforms for amplifying the voices of marginalised women, with The Girls Table leveraging its own channels to ensure their narratives resonate widely.

4. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=W-ek3AmZGiE>

Case 7 Analysis Table	
Issue	Acute water shortages in Tsholotsho and the lack of participation of young women in discussions and decision-making processes related to water scarcity and service delivery.
Convenor	The Girls Table
Date	April 2023
Mechanism	Question and answer Roundtable discussion
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Young women from Tsholotsho, Plumtree and Bulawayo • Bulawayo Progressive Residents Association (BUPRA) • The Girls Table
Structure and composition	The Girls Table curated the involvement of young women from different communities in Bulawayo, where they took part in a discussion on the water crisis. The girls shared their diverse experiences, while an expert from BUPRA provided insights into their rights, offered advice and suggested actionable strategies. The dialogue was recorded and subsequently broadcast on The Girls Table online platforms, making it accessible for other young women and stakeholders to watch and engage with.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The talk show platform provided an opportunity for young women to actively discuss water shortages in their community and contribute their voices to the ongoing discourse. • The young women received education and empowerment, learning effective methods to engage with their communities and leaders on pressing issues. • The Girls Table provided training to the young women on dialogue and facilitation techniques, as well as digital media and information literacy skills. • Several of the young women have emerged as community champions, taking the lead in continuing the conversation within their communities and ensuring the dialogue persists.
Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the young women lacked media training and had a limited understanding of the positive impact that virtual platforms can have, leading to hesitation in fully engaging with them. • Some were resistant to being labelled as activists by other participants.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Young women were motivated to join virtual discussions and received training on safe, responsible use of social media, enhancing their confidence in using these platforms securely and privately. • The involvement of BUPRA, which enabled the sharing of knowledge between the urban residents' association and the young women, facilitated effective engagement.

Case 8: Ending Child Marriage – Chiredzi’s Commitment

A Zimbabwe Peace Project facilitator leading a dialogue in Chiredzi.

The Constitution of Zimbabwe states that anyone below the age of 18 is a minor. The Constitutional Court has affirmed the prohibition of marrying anyone under the age of 18. Despite this, child marriages remain prevalent in many religious and cultural sectors, affecting girls as young as 12. Socio-economic challenges contribute to the rise in cases. Zimbabwe has one of the highest rates of child marriage in Africa, with more than 20 percent of girls aged 15 to 18 years currently in a union or marriage.⁵

The Zimbabwe Peace Project (ZPP), an organisation committed to promoting peace and advancing progressive solutions in communities through dialogue and advocacy on human rights issues, has been actively engaged in the Chiredzi community since 2017. It has facilitated dialogues on issues such as domestic violence, substance use and human rights. Conversations surrounding child marriages emerged after years of trust-building with community members, who came to perceive ZPP as an impartial interlocutor.

Through a series of dialogues on the issue of child marriage initiated in 2017, the community has committed to a zero-tolerance approach and resolved to rescue any girls who become child brides. In 2021, ZPP reported facilitating the rescue of seven girls from marriages.⁶ These rescue efforts were initiated by community members themselves, with ZPP being notified when funding and support were required. Former ZPP Director Jestina Mukoko attributes the organisation’s success in Chiredzi to building relationships, respecting traditional leadership structures, and obtaining full support from local leaders. Village heads have been active participants in the dialogues, recognising the value of ZPP’s initiatives.

5. UNICEF, September 2022, *Transforming Masculinities for Gender Equality and End to Child Marriage*, [Online] Available at: [\[4\]](#).

6. The Zimbabwe Peace Project, December 2021, *Zimbabwe Peace Project 2021 Annual Report*. [Online] Available at: [\[5\]](#).

Mukoko recounted an incident where local police and state security agents interrupted a meeting, questioning ZPP facilitators and participants about their agenda. Despite ZPP having obtained police clearance, the police attempted to disband the meeting. The village head intervened, engaging with the officials as the community's leader, and successfully advocated for the meeting to continue for the benefit of the community.

Furthermore, ZPP has empowered community champions, who are now responsible for driving conversations and initiatives in their areas. This approach has enabled the community to take ownership of their problems and sustain the success of the initiative. Mukoko emphasised that ZPP's role has transitioned to providing resources for implementation, as the community champions now convene meetings and obtain police clearance independently, showcasing the initiative's self-sufficiency and sustainability.

Case 8 Analysis Table	
Issue	Child marriage in Chiredzi, which persists despite being prohibited by Zimbabwean law.
Convenor	Zimbabwe Peace Project (ZPP)
Date	2017 – present
Mechanism	Consultation
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community members • Village head • ZPP
Structure and composition	ZPP initiated the process by facilitating consultative meetings and conducting education and awareness-raising campaigns with community leaders and residents. Additionally, ZPP involved the village head and provides updates on progress made.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ongoing conversation on child marriage has resulted in education and awareness-raising campaigns within the community. • A number of community members have taken a stand against child marriage, resolving to rescue any girl subjected to such unions. • A support system has been established that facilitates and sustains rescue efforts initiated by the community.
Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Child marriage is entrenched as an accepted cultural and religious norm in some contexts, resulting in resistance to address it. • In certain cases, an arranged child marriage can occur with the consent of parents, leading some to perceive the issue as a private family matter rather than a broader societal concern.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust was built on less sensitive issues before tackling child marriage, easing into more complex discussions. • Emphasis was placed on the illegality and rights violations of child marriage under Zimbabwean law to highlight its seriousness. • Community champions were identified to foster local ownership, facilitating dialogue and rescue missions. • ZPP's multifaceted strategy and community ownership played crucial roles in addressing child marriage effectively. • A robust, locally driven support system was key for the success of rescue efforts.

Case 9: Nkulumane Resolution – Vendors vs. Bulawayo City Council

Nkulumane informal traders engaging in conversation with VISET staff and Bulawayo City Council officials.

The Vendors Initiative for Socio-Economic Transformation (VISET) convened a multi-stakeholder consultative meeting in Bulawayo's Nkulumane Ward in August 2022. The meeting aimed at facilitating dialogue between informal traders and officials from the Bulawayo City Council.

VISET, a union of informal traders with a nationwide presence, ensures that informal traders have a voice in shaping inclusive cities. Through its initiatives, VISET promotes transparency and accountability between informal traders and key stakeholders. At the meeting, VISET provided a crucial platform for constructive engagement, fostering objective and informed exchanges between the two parties. Recognising a communication and understanding gap between informal traders and City Council officials, VISET Executive Director Samuel Wadzanai emphasised the necessity of building relationships whilst facilitating engagement.

The dialogue addressed various issues, with the importance of formalisation at the centre. Clashes between law enforcement officers and informal vendors were highlighted, resulting in confiscation of wares from the vendors. Both VISET and City Council officials explained the formalisation process for vending, emphasising how registration would ensure compliance with the law and afford vendors the benefits and protection enjoyed by licensed traders. The City Council reiterated its inability to engage with unlicensed vendors. The call for vendors to register and license their operations garnered broad support, leading to an increase in registered vendors.

Informal traders voiced their challenges, including the lack of water and ablution facilities, shortage of designated trading zones, and issues surrounding fines and confiscation of their wares. Amkelwe Nyathi, an informal trader, described the meeting as enlightening, providing him with a better understanding of his constitutional rights and Bulawayo City Council by-laws.

VISET's convening power emerged as a key success factor to the dialogue, managing power dynamics that hindered previous attempts at dialogue between traders and the City Council. VISET facilitated constructive conversations, thereby opening doors for continued engagement.

VISET continues to lead and facilitate conversations between Bulawayo's informal traders and decision-makers, to enable sustainable solutions for the informal trade sector. VISET's activities are not just limited to the city of Bulawayo. A large percentage of Zimbabweans have turned to the informal sector as the national economy has become largely informal. VISET is actively engaging municipalities countrywide for similar ward- and city-level dialogues with their respective constituents.

Case 9 Analysis Table	
Issue	Communication and understanding gaps between informal traders and officials from the Bulawayo City Council regarding issues such as formalisation processes, law enforcement practices, trading regulations and access to essential facilities like water and ablution facilities.
Convenor	Vendors Initiative for Socio-Economic Transformation (VISET)
Date	August 2022
Mechanism	Consultation
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VISET • Bulawayo City Council officials • Vendors
Structure and composition	A roundtable discussion facilitated by VISET with presentations from VISET and the Bulawayo City Council that were followed by question-and-answer and open discussion sessions.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A solidified platform for constant engagement among duty bearers and vendors. • An increased quality and quantity of internal dialogue among vendors. • An increased number of trader registrations with the City Council.
Barriers and challenges	Tensions between the vendors and the Bulawayo City Council, as vendors came to the meeting aggrieved about how they had been treated in the past.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VISET, a known civil society organisation for informal traders, played the role of a mediator, clarifying misunderstandings and focusing on building consensus among parties, was instrumental in reducing tensions and fostering mutual understanding. • VISET's ability to convene all relevant stakeholders for dialogue played a crucial role.

Case 10: Mambo Township's Water Crisis Response

In 2019, members of the Mambo community approached Zimbabwe African National Union Patriotic Front (ZANU-PF) Ward 7 Councillor Stanford Mukotami, seeking decisive action on the persistent water shortages in the area. Residents grappled with chronic water scarcity, exacerbated by outdated infrastructure that suffered blockages and frequent breakdowns. Despite repeated attempts to engage with Gweru City Council officials, residents saw little improvement. Budget constraints cited by the City Council further hampered service delivery.

To tackle the issue, Mukotami initiated meetings to propose a solution for the area. Initially, attendance at these dialogues was low, with fatigued residents expressing frustration over the lack of tangible outcomes from previous service delivery meetings. Mukotami's efforts to secure a donor willing to fund a borehole were met with scepticism, as past promises from donors had fallen through. However, Mukotami emphasised the need for community involvement, as the donor required the community to take responsibility for maintaining the borehole once installed.

Resident Carol Mupanguri joined in the initial scepticism, noting that many had grown weary of empty promises from political parties, local authorities and donors alike. However, as the project began to demonstrate results, support for the initiative grew. Some community members formed committees to mobilise participation street by street, emerging as champions of the cause.

By the final meeting convened for the borehole project, participation had significantly increased, signalling a shift in community engagement. Mukotami facilitated discussions on the borehole's operation and the community members reached a consensus on their contributions towards security and electricity bills associated with the borehole.

Case 10 Analysis Table	
Issue	Inability of the Gweru City Council to effectively address chronic water shortages due to budget constraints and outdated infrastructure.
Convenor	Ward councillor
Date	2019 – 2020
Mechanism	Consultation
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ward councillor • Community members • Local government leaders
Structure and composition	The councillor led town hall meetings on the issue, with participation increasing from less than 15 residents to over 100 in the final meetings.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the community borehole. • A positive effect on residents' households and businesses. • An increased understanding among community members of their ability to drive positive outcomes.
Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some residents displayed apathy and scepticism towards the process. • Low attendance and participation due to lack of understanding and trust in the initiative.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges were tackled through focused, continuous efforts and by engaging community champions to boost participation and momentum. • Residents' initiative to form street groups for better accountability. • Effective use of social media by both the councillor and residents to communicate updates and progress.

Case 11: Challenge to Monetary Policy – Kadoma Business Community

KEDC on 8 April 2021

The Kadoma Economic Development Chamber (KEDC) was established in 2018 by outgoing councillor and businessman Langton Mabhanga to address local economic issues. It aimed to enhance private sector engagement with the city council and lobby for favourable policies at the local and national levels. This initiative is unique in Zimbabwe, as no other city has a dedicated economic chamber for local business concerns.

KEDC has played a crucial role in overcoming a common barrier faced by small cities or towns: limited access to key decision-makers, who are typically based in capital cities or head offices. Mabhanga noted that although regional representatives participate in dialogues, further consultations with more senior officials often prolong the process.

As a significant contributor to Zimbabwe's gold industry, Kadoma faced challenges when in 2020 the Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe (RBZ) mandated miners to surrender a percentage of their gold proceeds in local currency. Amidst an outcry from miners preferring USD payments due to the devaluation of the local currency, KEDC initiated a dialogue with government and RBZ officials. KEDC successfully convinced senior RBZ officials to travel to Kadoma for discussions. Following a robust engagement, the RBZ governor committed to reviewing the policy, leading to a policy change within seven days.

KEDC has fostered a vibrant culture of business dialogue in Kadoma, launching a Women's Chapter to mobilise community participation in various initiatives. It regularly hosts consultative meetings with businesses to address matters such as the annual budget and intervention planning. Overall, KEDC has become an institutional platform for progressive local business dialogue.

Case 11 Analysis Table	
Issue	A directive from the Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe (RBZ), issued in its 2020 monetary policy statement, which adversely impacted players in the local gold industry.
Convenor	Kadoma Economic Development Chamber (KEDC)
Date	August 2020
Mechanism	Mediation
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RBZ • Fidelity Printers • KEDC • Ministry of State • Kadoma mining companies
Structure and composition	KEDC convened and moderated town hall meetings attended by about 120 participants.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes to RBZ's monetary policy and retention rates on the surrendered gold. • A vibrant culture of business dialogue in Kadoma, including launching a Women's Chapter and regularly hosting consultative meetings with business leaders. • KEDC established itself as an institutional platform for progressive local business dialogue. • Increased confidence among community members in approaching leaders and policymakers for audience and platforms.
Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants expressed concerns about officials being defensive and not open to criticism during the preliminary stages of the conversation. • An initial reluctance among participants to candidly speak out on issues involving sensitive information (e.g., gold smuggling).
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitators balanced power dynamics by having government officials listen before speaking, ensuring a focus on information gathering rather than enforcement actions. • The involvement of key decision-makers facilitated quick decisions and implementations. • Success was furthered by effective stakeholder communication, proactive involvement of KEDC, and fostering a safe space for open dialogue.

Case 12: Crime Resolution in a Harare Neighbourhood

A Sentosa Neighbourhood Watch patrol team.

Sentosa Neighbourhood Watch (SNW) in Harare emerged in 2018 when a local electricity substation was vandalised, leaving the community without power for weeks. A resident's initiative rallied the community for a successful fundraising effort to repair the substation. This success catalysed a highly motivated and committed community group, driven by the shared goal of creating a safe neighbourhood.

Situated in the west of Harare, Sentosa is a multiracial, upper middle-class suburb known for its peaceful ambiance. The SNW leadership team, comprising dedicated volunteers and officers, meets regularly to strategise. The broader community engages primarily through a WhatsApp group boasting 260 members.

During its formative stages, positive momentum fuelled by the substation repair success and volunteerism led community leaders to realise the need for a more sustainable structure. A dialogue at the local church saw 30 community members gathering to discuss formalising SNW's operations. Residents pledged US\$10 each to fund a nightly patrol team, a decision later endorsed by others on the WhatsApp group. The residents clearly articulated their goal of reducing crime by at least 50 percent and committed to ensuring the substation was never damaged again.

Over the past four years, the patrol team has significantly reduced crime, with no further incidents of substation vandalism. However, engaging over 200 individuals presents challenges. Carol Weare, SNW's current leader, acknowledges the difficulty, necessitating vetting procedures due to past infiltration by criminals.

Bryan Strang, head of the patrol team, acknowledges the need for greater participation but emphasises the impact of committed individuals. Strang also highlights the team's relationship with the Zimbabwe Republic Police as a key stakeholder. The patrol team collaborates with the Mabelreign Police Station, which provides support to SNW. There is an open line of communication between the two parties. Despite challenges, SNW has fostered a greater sense of unity among residents,

uncommon in urban areas. However, attempts to expand its mandate, for example by initiating road repairs, have faced funding and support issues, leading to a focus on core activities.

Overall, SNW continues to promote community dialogue and safety, embodying a spirit of collaboration and vigilance.

Case 12 Analysis Table	
Issue	Security challenges in Sentosa, including the vandalism of an electricity substation.
Convenor	Community leader
Date	April – June 2018
Mechanism	Consultation
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community members • Zimbabwe Republic Police
Structure and composition	Community leaders convened a meeting at the local church to outline the vision for the neighbourhood watch and garner resident support. Attendees proposed action items and agreed on next steps and a monthly financial contribution. Resolutions were then shared via a community WhatsApp group, through which over 200 residents endorsed the decisions.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formalisation and establishment of a neighbourhood watch programme with a leadership structure and patrol teams. • Agreement among residents to contribute US\$10 monthly to fund neighbourhood watch activities. • Recognition of the need to address other community issues, fostering a commitment to collective action.
Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relatively low participation in meetings and fund contributions considering the neighbourhood's total population. • Disparity in commitment levels between homeowners and tenants, with homeowners showing more dedication. • Cordial and engaging in-person meetings contrasting with potentially hostile exchanges on the virtual platform.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residents moved forward with the resources and participants at hand, not waiting for perfect conditions. • The leadership actively engaged key community figures, highlighting the value of their involvement for neighbourhood preservation. • Success was driven by a committed team of compensated volunteers, fostering community unity and sustained action. • A strong virtual presence through a WhatsApp group facilitated transparency and daily engagement. • Coordination was enhanced by regular, conveniently located meetings and a well-defined protocol for neighbourhood patrols.

Artisanal mining activity at Redwing Mine.

Case 13: Penhalonga Confronts Mining Company

Redwing Mine, situated in Penhalonga, Manicaland Province, is a bustling gold operation partially owned by Better Brands Mining that attracts numerous artisanal and small-scale miners. Despite its significant contributions to Zimbabwe's gold reserves, the mine has faced severe challenges, notably the recording of over 21 fatalities within 13 months by 2023.⁷ The tipping point came in January 2023, when the Zimbabwe government's Environmental Management Agency (EMA) ordered the mine's closure due to escalating fatalities, security issues and environmental hazards.⁸

The Centre for Natural Resource Governance (CNRG), an advocacy organisation, has been actively involved in Penhalonga since 2012, defending community rights affected by extractive industries. CNRG Deputy Programme Manager Tracy Mutowekuziva highlighted its role in educating residents about their rights and advocating for safer mining practices. Despite CNRG's efforts, community members often struggle to navigate the appropriate channels for addressing grievances.

Community activist Loveness Kachingwe, who received training from CNRG, shed light on the dire consequences of irresponsible mining practices, including widespread dust pollution, hazardous pits that endanger residents and livestock, and water contamination by cyanide and mercury.⁹ Despite forming a committee to engage the EMA regarding the dust issue, they were met with a disappointing response.

7. The Herald, 26 January 2023, EMA Closes Redwing Mine. [Online] Available at: [\[6\]](#).

8. The Business Weekly, 25 January 2023, Government shuts down Better Brands Mine. [Online] Available at [\[7\]](#).

9. The Centre for Natural Resources Governance, February 2023, CNRG Renew Calls for Transparent Safe Accountable Mining as Deaths in Zimbabwe Increase. [Online] Available at: [\[8\]](#).

In response to the crisis, CNRG intensified its engagement in Penhalonga, drawing attention to the issue through training and awareness-raising meetings attended by respected traditional leader Chief James Kurauone Mutasa. With CNRG's assistance, residents petitioned several Parliamentary Portfolio Committees, leading to on-site inspections and a subsequent report by the Committee on Defence, Home Affairs, and Security Services.¹⁰

Mutasa's involvement and CNRG's support proved instrumental in mediating dialogues between the mine's management and residents following the closure. While mining activity has resumed with some improvements, such as enhanced regulation and restricted areas due to unstable ground, fatalities persist, leaving the community dissatisfied.

The residents of Penhalonga remain committed to ongoing dialogue with the mine's management, striving for a balance where they can benefit from mining activities without enduring the consequences of unchecked operations.

Case 13 Analysis Table	
Issue	Adverse impacts of irresponsible mining practices, including fatalities, environmental hazards and the endangerment of residents and livestock.
Convenor	Centre for Natural Resource Governance (CNRG)
Date	2017 – present
Mechanism	Mediation
Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CNRG • Penhalonga residents • Environmental Management Agency • Artisanal and small-scale miners
Structure and composition	CNRG orchestrated a series of consultative dialogues, initially centred on skills enhancement for the community, which attracted participation from community activists and artisanal miners. With the escalation of crises, the dialogues evolved to concentrate on assembling key leaders and empowering community members to initiate meaningful dialogues with crucial stakeholders.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heightened awareness and advocacy for safer mining practices among residents, empowering them with knowledge about their rights and effective channels for addressing grievances. • Continued on-site inspections and comprehensive reports highlighting the community's challenges and underscoring the necessity for regulatory interventions. • Penhalonga residents' commitment to ongoing dialogue with the mine's management.

10. Parliamentary Committee on Defence, Home Affairs and Security Services, September 2022, *The Security of Minerals: Illicit Trading in Minerals and Mineral leakages*. [Online] Available at [\[9\]](#).

Barriers and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motivating artisanal miners proved challenging due to their demanding operations and lack of time for training sessions. • Meetings often became polarised, leading to tensions between individuals benefitting from mining activities and those adversely affected by environmental and social consequences. • Political sensitivities surrounding the operation’s issues heightened caution among authorities, limiting their willingness to approve meetings and actively engage in dialogues.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CNRG fostered positive relationships with authorities, collaborating to uphold law and order and environmental standards. • CNRG advocated for reconciliation and cooperation through non-inflammatory language. • Community activists were key in mobilising and sustaining dialogue. • Training workshops led by CNRG introduced constructive language for discussing mining impacts. • Community leaders and chiefs played a critical, behind-the-scenes role in managing power dynamics between the mine’s leadership and political players. • Extensive training and engagement prepared the community for mediation. • Broad media coverage of the issues provided leverage for advocating solutions.

IV. Key Findings

This section synthesises the findings from the analyses of the above community-level dialogues and extracts key lessons specific to the Zimbabwean experience. The lessons highlight the importance of effective convening, inclusive participation, and strategic planning. They underscore the need for strong local leadership, technical support, continuous engagement to sustain the dialogue, and contextualising the process to the cultural and social dynamics of the specific community. The findings are structured around the various stages of the process, from initiation and planning to execution and follow-up.

Dialogue pre-conditions, scope and context

- **Contextualisation:** Before taking any action, it is crucial to understand the social norms and culture of a specific community to avoid any offensive or inappropriate behaviour, language or approach to maintain a positive dialogue atmosphere. Community dialogue initiatives in Zimbabwe can fail if they are not tailored to fit the community and participant needs. (See: [Language and Disability Conversations in Mbare](#) and [Ending Child Marriage – Chiredzi’s Commitment](#).)
- **Getting started:** Waiting for the perfect moment, including waiting for financial resources, can hinder dialogue. Often, it is better to “start with what you have”. Communities typically need to address issues in real time, and they can learn and adapt along the way. Proceeding this way also fosters momentum, encourages a culture of action, and can lead to early results that attract additional support. (See: [Crime Resolution in Harare Neighbourhood](#) and [Language and Disability Conversations in Mbare](#).)

Dialogue convenors

- **Convening power:** Individuals outside of leadership structures or organisations often lack the convening power and typically need to defer this role to an established institution or trusted actor to ensure adequate participation. This is a more efficient approach than trying to build convening power from scratch. (See: [Penhalonga Confronts Mining Company](#) and [Nkulumane Resolution: Vendors vs. Bulawayo Council](#).)
- **Effective convenors:** It is important to find trusted convenors who will remain involved throughout in order to guarantee success of the dialogue. Zimbabwe has a number of institutions that have a demonstrated record of such reliability, though the right choice (e.g., church, NGOs, traditional leaders, etc.) depends on the case. (See: [Ending Child Marriage – Chiredzi’s Commitment](#).)
- **Technical support:** Convenors at local level sometimes lack the necessary technical skills to successfully facilitate community dialogues. Failing to inte-

grate the required skills is a missed opportunity, especially given the financial support available for community dialogue initiatives. Capacity building and technical assistance can enhance the effectiveness of the dialogue process and ensure that discussions are well-structured, inclusive, and results-oriented. (See: [Economic Zone Ignites Leather Value Chain Talk in Bulawayo.](#))

Dialogue actors

- **Stakeholder engagement:** Early involvement of stakeholders speeds up decision-making and promotes ownership of both the process and outcomes of dialogue. Likewise, it ensures that the solutions are practical and have institutional support; helps identify potential challenges in advance; and enhances transparency, trust, and accountability within the dialogue process. (See: [Challenge to Monetary Policy – Kadoma Business Community](#) and [Enhancing Early Childhood Development Policies in Harare.](#))
- **Role of community leaders:** Community leaders must be actively engaged from the outset, as they are crucial not only in the initiation phase (e.g., shaping the issues and convening participants) but also in mobilising residents, acting as effective communication channels, shaping narratives, fostering a culture of dialogue, and implementing solutions. Their significant convening power and trustworthiness, especially in rural communities in Zimbabwe, makes them indispensable in sustaining dialogues and ensuring the outcomes are realised. (See: [School Fees in Domboshava.](#))
- **Role of local NGOs:** Local NGOs in Zimbabwe, with their deep-rooted connections within communities, are valuable facilitators of dialogue initiatives. Their ability to navigate complex power dynamics and provide or mobilise the necessary financial and technical expertise makes them invaluable. Partnering with them ensures that engagement is maximised, participation fatigue is prevented, and stakeholders' voices are heard. (See: [Ending Child Marriage – Chiredzi's Commitment](#) and [Empowering Girls – Tsholotsho Service Delivery Dialogues.](#))
- **Role of community champions:** Community champions mobilise residents and serve as effective communication channels during dialogue processes. They shape narratives outside the formal dialogue and perpetuate the culture of dialogue within the community. (See: [Mambo Township's Water Crisis Response.](#))

Dialogue structure and framework

- **Planning and agenda setting:** Agendas should be set through a process of prior consultations with key stakeholders. When agendas are unilaterally decided by the convenor this can lead to misalignment. Convenors must

adapt and adjust the agenda to address the issues as new concerns or ideas emerge. (See: [Empowering Epworth's Youth – Dialogues for Change.](#))

- **Vision casting:** An early phase of envisioning the desired outcome and ideal community result by all stakeholders is a powerful way of fostering unity among dialogue participants and painting a picture of a positive shared destiny. A shared vision with clearly outlined objectives will drive the actions required for success. (See: [Crime Resolution in Harare Neighbourhood.](#))
- **Dialogue format:** The context and issues being addressed must determine the dialogue format (i.e., the form should follow the function). Consultations and roundtable discussions are favourable for drawing out views and town halls are effective for allowing communities to engage with leaders. Convenors must recognise when mediation needs to occur to align opposing views. (See: [Nkulumane Resolution – Vendors vs. Bulawayo Council.](#))
- **Facilitation and moderation** – If not already skilled and experienced, convenors must be trained on effective dialogue and facilitation techniques and have a comprehensive understanding of different dialogue mechanisms and frameworks to understand when to use them and how to steer conversations. (see: [Empowering Epworth's Youth – Dialogues for Change.](#))
- **Location:** Conducting dialogues in safe, familiar environments fosters openness and effective communication. This is especially true if polarisation is high or if there are significant power dynamics at play. When participants feel secure and comfortable in their surroundings, they are more likely to engage honestly and constructively. If participants come from far away and require transportation, rotating the location or reverting to virtual platforms (barring limited accessibility) can be beneficial. (See: [Challenge to Monetary Policy – Kadoma Business Community.](#))
- **Transparency:** The Zimbabwean context is highly securitised, thus any dialogue is subject to scrutiny and convenings may require certain steps to be taken prior to a meeting (e.g., informing the police for gatherings). Appropriate notification and approval processes must be followed, and such notification and approval must be communicated for maximum participation. (See: [Penhalonga Confronts Mining Company.](#))
- **Use of digital platforms:** Virtual platforms offer effective channels for dialogue and may increase participation and facilitate the voices of marginalised communities. Live streaming can bring transparency and accountability and enhance public understanding of governance processes. (See: [Empowering Girls – Tsholotsho Service Delivery Dialogues](#) and [Rimuka's Flood Solution Journey.](#))

Participation and inclusivity

- **Diversity and representation:** Dialogues in Zimbabwe must ensure diversity and inclusion to capture the experiences and perspectives of all groups. Excluding key groups can lead to frustration and apathy, ultimately undermining the dialogue's effectiveness. Ensuring the representation of various demographics, including women, minority groups and marginalised communities is essential for a holistic understanding of the issues at hand. Dialogues must particularly include those affected the most by the issue. (See: [Empowering Girls – Tsholotsho Service Delivery Dialogues](#).)
- **Youth centring:** Inclusivity should ideally extend to children and youth, who possess valuable insights and new ideas and whose participation is crucial in implementing change. Consolidating a sense of ownership and commitment among all participants, especially young people, enriches the discussions and leads to more sustainable outcomes. (See: [Empowering Epworth's Youth – Dialogues for Change](#).)
- **Skills:** Investing in skills and capacity building for community members can encourage participation and enhance their participation in the dialogue process and implementation of outcomes. It empowers community members to grow their independence and initiate dialogues without any assistance. (See: [Penhalonga Confronts Mining Company](#).)

Addressing barriers and challenges

- **Anticipation of barriers:** In any dialogue, it is not a question of “if”, but rather “when”, the barriers to the process will emerge. They may include apathy, logistical or financial constraints, polarisation and in some cases a resistance to addressing long-standing societal norms. (See: [Ending Child Marriage – Chiredzi's Commitment](#).)
- **Overcoming barriers:** Overcoming barriers requires sustained trust-building efforts and a focus on shared concerns. Addressing challenges arising from polarised identities can be achieved by emphasising common interests and ensuring that the benefits of dialogue are fairly distributed. By proactively addressing such barriers, communities can create a more cohesive and collaborative environment conducive to meaningful dialogue. (See: [Language and Disability Conversations in Mbare](#) and [Mambo Township's Water Crisis Response](#).)

Implementing dialogue outcomes

- **Post-dialogue communication:** Communication after the dialogue is vital to share the status of implementation of resolutions. Emails, social media and messaging are the most popular and efficient means to communicate impor-

tant updates to those unable to attend in person. By leveraging these digital tools, communities can foster more inclusive and continuous engagement, bridging gaps and fostering a more informed and participatory approach to implementation. (See: [The Girls Table convenes meeting with young women in Tsholotsho on voting rights.](#))

- **Post dialogue actions** – Action and follow-up items should be articulated and those responsible for implementation should be capacitated. Convenors are not always implementers, and the transfer of responsibility has been found to stall progress, especially where implementing actors have been passive and shunned responsibility and ownership. (See: [Language and Disability Conversations in Mbare.](#))

Sustaining long-term change

- **Assessing dialogue impact:** A robust mechanism to evaluate the impact of a dialogue is required yet is sometimes overlooked in community dialogues. The vision-casting process and articulation of key objectives serves as a basis to create metrics and targets for monitoring and evaluation. (See: [Crime Resolution in Harare Neighbourhood](#) and [Challenge to Monetary Policy – Kadoma Business Community.](#))
- **Community ownership:** Community buy-in is critical for the long-term success of dialogue initiatives and for ensuring the implementation of agreements. Sustaining dialogue efforts through continuous engagement with leaders and community champions promotes a culture of dialogue and moves the community away from a donor dependency mindset. (See: [Mambo Township’s Water Crisis Response](#) and [Ending Child Marriage – Chiredzi’s Commitment.](#))
- **Collaborations:** Multiple organisations may be working on similar issues. Collaborations and partnerships enhance outcomes whilst allowing for a more multi-pronged, joined-up approach to issues. (See: [Enhancing Early Childhood Development Policies in Harare.](#))
- **Improving the visibility and appeal of dialogue:** It is important that communities are aware of ongoing efforts in their area to promote a culture of dialogue. Those leading the initiatives should try to visit places where community members often gather and start conversations. They can spark interest in dialogue outcomes by using tools like theatre to capture attention and convey a particular message. (See: [Language and Disability Conversations in Mbare](#) and [Empowering Epworth’s Youth – Dialogues for Change.](#))

V. Enhancing Community and National-level Dialogue

Having regard to the findings and lessons from this study, below is a summary framework meant to clarify, enhance and promote the culture of dialogue in Zimbabwe.

1. Framework for Enhancing and Promoting Community dialogue in Zimbabwe

Preconditions, scope and context	Dialogue convenors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand social norms and community issues before initiating any dialogue • Identify suitable entry point and conversation starters • Just get started - even when conditions are not ideal • Prioritise topics with widespread community interest to galvanise support • Address topics in the window of relevance and opportunity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify centres of power and trust in communities • Support convenors with technical skills to address skills gaps • Ensure facilitators and moderators are trained in the various techniques
Dialogue actors	Structure and framework
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage all stakeholders early • Ensure community leaders are actively involved • Identify institutional partners with deep roots and connections in the communities • Identify community champions to mobilise participation and shape narratives • Incorporate training and awareness campaigns to improve civic competencies of individuals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set agendas through pre-consultations and validate agenda with participants at start • Incorporate a period of vision casting to initiate the process • Choose a dialogue format that matches the goals and issues at hand • Select strategic locations to ensure accessibility and effective participation • Enhance dialogue process with use of digital platforms

Participation and inclusivity	Addressing barriers and challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure all demographics, including women, minority groups and marginalised communities, are represented • Tailor interventions to capture youth voices in an age-appropriate manner 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anticipate barriers such as apathy, logistical or financial constraints, polarisation and a resistance to societal change • Proactively address any barriers before they permanently stall the initiative • Focus on shared concerns and clearly highlight fair benefits to address apathy and polarisation • Prepare for long term engagement to address societal issues • Seek partnerships to address financial or logistical barriers
Implementing outcomes	Sustaining long-term change
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure strategic post- dialogue communication to solidify resolutions and results • Disseminate post- dialogue resolutions widely to the community • Initiate activities and resolutions with a focus on stakeholder support and buy-in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build on community buy-in and ownership for long- term outcomes, particularly once NGOs and other partners exit • Seek collaborations and partnerships for multi-pronged sustainable efforts • Foster continued engagement within community as a foundation for perpetuating dialogue and sustained success

2. Recommendations for Enhancing National-Level Dialogue in Zimbabwe

Findings from this research indicate that community-level dialogues can be used to catalyse national-level conversations in Zimbabwe through two mechanisms. The first is a community-anchored (bottom-up) approach that escalates dialogue from the community to national level. The second is a horizontal approach that sees an issue discussed and replicated through multiple communities to reach national relevance.

a. The community-anchored approach to catalysing national-level efforts

A community-anchored approach is one that involves identifying issues and escalating them in sequence from the ward level to the district and provincial level and eventually escalating to the national level. Applying such a principle allows national conversations to start at the bottom and culminates in conversations at the highest level informed by the unique views and perspectives of the citizens and residents. This approach allows the social legitimacy that dialogue has at the community level to be instilled at the national level.

Bottom-up approach for inclusive, participatory national-level dialogue

Local initiatives cannot upscale themselves. However, they can be multiplied for national relevance. Therefore, a robust structure is needed to facilitate the required escalation and convergence process. A coalition of local networks that coordinates actors across regions and issues is one way to facilitate the escalation of issues through multiple levels.

b. The horizontal intensification and replication approach to catalysing national-level efforts

Outcomes from a community-level dialogue can also gain significant momentum through horizontal intensification and replication. The same issues can be addressed continually and consistently by mobilising civil society organisations and other relevant institutions to initiate the same local dialogue on a nationwide scale.

This approach will similarly require a robust structure or strong institution to coordinate and implement.

Whichever pathway is chosen, the following cross-cutting lessons from community dialogue can be used to enrich national-level dialogue processes in Zimbabwe:

- **Identifying strategic entry points and locations for dialogue** – Well-respected organisations with strong community ties, local elected leaders and traditional leaders are vital entry points for dialogue initiatives. Location also matters and there is strategic advantage in starting national conversations in locations with a historical or economic significance to the dialogue.
- **Focusing on galvanising issues** – Communities are willing to rally and act on issues that affect their daily lives and will participate in processes that will bring changes they are seeking. Identifying such issues can catalyse dialogue and promote participation. Despite racial divides and polarisation,

communities can unite around common causes, demonstrating the potential for inclusivity and collaboration and reduced tensions.

- **Using community champions to drive positive narratives** – Community activists, influential elders and other recognised local champions were found to be important ambassadors of key messages. National dialogue can incorporate such community champions to foster broad engagement and build a positive narrative about dialogue and its utility for achieving useful social and economic results.

A broad-based civic platform in Zimbabwe could play a key role in taking forward these and other lessons of this study, building inclusive dialogue nationally from what already exists in robust form locally.

VI. Annex

A. Interview Framework

- 1. Context, Pre-conditions and Scope of the Dialogue**
 - a. Why was the dialogue convened?
 - b. Who convened the dialogue?
 - c. How was the agenda of the dialogue set?
 - d. How long did it last?
 - e. Has the convenor organised other dialogues?
 - f. Where and when did the dialogue occur?
 - g. Who met any associated expenses?
 - h. Is there already a culture of dialogue around this issue?

- 2. Participation and Inclusivity**
 - a. How many people participated in the dialogue?
 - b. How were the participants selected and informed about the dialogue?
 - c. Are there any key stakeholders who did not participate in the dialogue? If so, what were the reasons for non-participation?
 - d. Were any participants compensated financially for their role in the dialogue?

- 3. Barriers to Dialogue**
 - a. Was there any resistance, objections or opposition to the dialogue? If so from whom and why?
 - b. How were any spoilers or barriers addressed or resolved?
 - c. Are there any issues that undermined the dialogue and led to certain issues being abandoned?

- 4. Dialogue Structure and Framework**
 - a. Was the dialogue held in private or in public?
 - b. How was the dialogue structured (e.g., negotiation, panel discussion, town hall, Q&A, roundtable)?
 - c. Who facilitated, moderated or led the discussion? How was the facilitator selected?
 - d. Are there any stakeholders who stayed silent?
 - e. What was the tone of engagement – cordial or heated?

5. Critical Success Factors

- a.** Was the primary objective of the dialogue achieved?
- b.** Were there any unintended outcomes (either positive or negative)?
- c.** Were the outcomes and agreed action points from the dialogue executed?
In what time frame?

6. Post – Dialogue Outcomes

- a.** Was there immediate follow-up communication with the participants after the dialogue summarising/describing the dialogue and outcomes?
- b.** Have there been any challenges with ensuring stakeholders remain accountable to doing what was agreed in the dialogue? How has this been addressed?
- c.** What were the key learnings from the dialogue about convening and stakeholder engagement?
- d.** What would the convenor do differently next time?
- e.** Was the dialogue covered by any media?

7. Long-term Impact

- a.** How has the conversation around the dialogue's focus issue continued?
- b.** What is the status of the issue 1, 2 or 3 years later?

B. List of Interviewees

Name	Case	Organisation	Date	Actor	Interview
Amkelwe Nyathi	Case 9: Nkulumane Resolution – Vendors vs. Bulawayo Council (2022)	Bulawayo Trader	8/23	Participant	Virtual
Bryan Strang	Case 12: Crime Resolution in Harare Neighbourhood (2018)	Sentosa Neighbourhood Watch	7/23	Participant	In-person
Carol Mupanguri	Case 10: Mambo Township's Water Crisis Response (2019-2020)	Ward 7 Resident	8/23	Participant	Virtual
Caroline Weare	Case 12: Crime Resolution in Harare Neighbourhood (2018)	Sentosa Neighbourhood Watch	7/23	Convenor	In-person
Chido Tavengwa	Case 5: Empowering Epworth's Youth – Dialogues for Change (2023)	Peer Educator	8/23	Participant	Virtual
Devin Levie	Case 6: Rimuka's Flood Solution Journey (2022)	CCC Councillor Ward 13	8/23	Convenor	In-person
Eunah Makaza	Case 6: Rimuka's Flood Solution Journey (2022)	Ward 13 Resident	8/23	Participant	In-person
Gear Hanyane	Case 11: Challenge to Monetary Policy – Kadoma Business Community (2020)	Former Director of Housing, Kadoma City Council	8/23	Participant	In-person
Hazvinei Mushonga	Case 4: Enhancing Early Childhood Development Policies in Harare (2019-2022)	ZINECDA	8/23	Participant	Virtual
Jacob Nyathi	Case 1: Economic Zone Ignites Leather Value Chain Talk in Bulawayo (2023)	ZLDC Secretary	8/23	Participant	Virtual
Jestina Mukoko	Case 8: Ending Child Marriage – Chiredzi's Commitment (2017-present)	Former Director, ZPP	8/23	Convenor	Virtual
Josephine Chibanda	Case 2: School Fees in Domboshava (2022)	Founder Victory Christian School	7/23	Convenor	In-person
Joyce Moyo	Case 6: Rimuka's Flood Solution Journey (2022)	CCC Councillor Ward 1	8/23	Convenor	In-person

Langton Mabhanga	Case 11: Challenge to Monetary Policy – Kadoma Business Community (2020)	KEDC Founder and Chairperson	8/23	Convenor	In-person
Loveness Kachingwe	Case 13: Penhalonga Confronts Mining Company (2021)	Community Activist	12/23	Participant	Virtual
Prosper Masibi	Case 9: Nkulumane Resolution – Vendors vs. Bulawayo Council (2022)	VISET Coordinator	8/23	Convenor	Virtual
Ratidzo Njagu	Case 5: Empowering Epworth’s Youth – Dialogues for Change (2023)	Kunashe Foundation	7/23	Convenor	In-person
Sandra Gama	Case 7: Empowering Girls – Tsholotsho Service Delivery Dialogues (2023)	Girls Table	8/23	Convenor	Virtual
Sikhonzeni Ndlovu	Case 7: Empowering Girls – Tsholotsho Service Delivery Dialogues (2023)	Tsholotsho Resident	8/23	Participant	Virtual
Stanford Mukotami	Case 10: Mambo Township’s Water Crisis Response (2019-2020)	ZANU PF Councillor Ward 7	8/23	Convenor	In-person
Thulani Ndlovu	Case 1: Economic Zone Ignites Leather Value Chain Talk in Bulawayo (2023)	Solidaridad	8/23	Convenor	Virtual
Tinashe Rutambo	Case 3: Language and Disability Conversations in Mbare (2023)	ZIDA	8/23	Convenor	Virtual
Tracy Mutowekuziva	Case 13: Penhalonga Confronts Mining Company (2021)	Centre for Natural Resource Governance	12/23	Convenor	In-person
Trevor Nyammubarwa	Case 3: Language and Disability Conversations in Mbare (2023)	I Am Zimbabwe Trust	8/23	Participant	Virtual
Yvonne Mpondi	Case 2: School Fees in Domboshava (2022)	School Parent	8/23	Participant	Virtual

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- Zimbabwe International Disability Association
- Zimbabwe Network of Early Childhood Development Actors
- Kunashe Foundation
- The Girls Table
- The Zimbabwe Peace Project
- The Sentosa Neighborhood Watch
- Kadoma Economic Development Chamber (KEDC)
- The Vendor’s Initiative for Socio-Economic Transformation

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